

STUDY OF THE LEVEL OF DOMESTIC TRAUMATISM AMONG SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN IN THE KHOREZM REGION

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Relevance: It is well known that children's bodies are in a stage of active development, making them more susceptible to various injuries. These injuries can negatively impact their physical and mental health, academic performance, and social activities, ultimately limiting their future opportunities. Additionally, they increase financial burdens on both the healthcare system and families. Therefore, studying the prevalence of domestic injuries among school-aged children and addressing this issue as a socially significant concern is of great importance.

Research Objective: To study and analyze the occurrence of domestic injuries among school-aged children in the Khorezm region. Based on the identified causes, to develop appropriate recommendations and preventive measures to reduce the incidence of such injuries.

Materials and Methods: For this study, data on injuries among school-aged children living in Urgench city, Yangiariq, and Qo'shko'pir districts of the Khorezm region from 2016 to 2020 were used as the primary material. Social-hygienic and sanitary-statistical methods were applied to analyze the findings.

Results and Discussion:

To study the prevalence of domestic injuries among children in the Khorezm region, one city (Urgench) and two rural districts (Ko'shko'pir and Yangiariq) were selected for analysis. The results showed that the injury rate in the studied areas was 24.65 ± 0.23 per 1,000 children.

Moreover, injuries among boys (40.94 ± 0.41) were found to be nearly six times higher than among girls (6.83 ± 0.18). This indicator was found to be 4.6 times higher among children aged 6–9 years, 5.6 times higher among those aged 10–14 years, and 8.1 times higher among those aged 15–17 years. This suggests that the medical and

social causes of domestic injuries among children require a more in-depth scientific analysis whenever possible. During the studied years, the prevalence of injuries among children in the region showed an increasing trend until 2019, with a particularly noticeable rise among boys (27%). However, among girls, the injury rate remained relatively stable. An analysis of injuries by age groups revealed that as children grew older, the incidence of injuries also increased. Among children aged 15–17 years (41.90 ± 0.63), the injury rate was found to be 2.2 times higher compared to those aged 6–9 years (18.70 ± 0.33).

Among children aged 10–14 years, this indicator was found to be 20.42 ± 0.33 . Notably, in all age groups, the prevalence of injuries among boys showed an increasing trend over the studied years. However, among girls, an increase was observed only in the 15–17 age group, while in the other age groups, the injury prevalence remained unchanged. Among the different types of injuries, mechanical injuries were the most common among school-aged children. In the majority of cases (two-thirds), this was attributed to inadequate living conditions in the areas where the children resided.

Conclusion: Based on the findings, it can be concluded that studying and analyzing the prevalence of domestic injuries among school-aged children, and developing appropriate recommendations, solutions, and preventive measures based on the collected data, serve as an essential program for ensuring the health and well-being of future generations.

